

RECENT ADVANCES IN THE CHEMISTRY OF SESQUITERPENES*

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Prior to the introduction of dehydrogenation as a tool in establishing the carbon framework of various alicyclic compounds, the structures of just a few sesquiterpenes had been known with any certainty. 'Ruzicka and his collaborators' are mainly responsible for the successful application of this method in settling the nuclear structure of various sesquiterpenes. Though active interest has been displayed in the field after that, the present decade has been especially fruitful, and at present the structures of several compounds are definitely established, and in some cases the finer details of the constitution have also been worked out. This report will cover the progress made during the period 1943-1952.

A careful perusal of the research work carried out over last several decades will reveal that the older methods of structure-determination have not been very successful either because the degradation products are too complex to admit of separation and identification or are too simple to throw any light on the original molecule. The most profitable researches centre round the newer methods of organic chemistry. *Dehydrogenation* has proved to be extremely useful in settling the structures of various sesquiterpenes, especially the bicyclic hydrocarbons and their derivatives. At present, on its basis, four well known groups are recognised, viz., cadalene, eudalene, guaiazulene and vetivazulene. Some compounds give rise to any one of these products as a result of simple dehydrogenation of the original bicyclic structure, while others may yield the same substance by dehydrogenation when either a ring-closure or a ring-fission has also occurred. Usually it is quite easy to differentiate if besides dehydrogenation any other reaction has also taken place. A very useful extension of the dehydrogenation method involves the technique of labelling a double bond with an additional methyl group, a process easily carried out by the interaction of the hydrocarbon epoxide with methylmagnesium iodide, followed by dehydration and dehydrogenation. This method was first employed by Ruzicka and Sternbach² in locating the nuclear double bond of *dextro*-pimaric acid. The process has been used with advantage in the case of *cadinene*³, *isozingiberene*⁴, *copaene*⁵ and a *cadinenic* sesquiterpene from the oil of *Hardwickia pinnata*⁶. All the the theoretically possible methylcadalenes⁷ have been synthesised in this laboratory. In the eudalene series, most of the required naphthalene derivatives were synthesised in connection with the location of the carbonyl group of tetrahydrocyperone⁸. Much more synthetic work will have to be carried out in the azulene series in order to get the alkyl derivatives of guaiazulene and vetivazulene which will ultimately serve as reference substances.

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Reduction carried out by sodium in liquid ammonia has also proved useful. Two aspects of this reduction procedure have given quite fruitful results on the synthetic side. Synthesis of β -curcumene⁹ makes use of this procedure for converting an aromatic system, easily accessible by usual synthetic methods, into the required dihydro derivative, which is otherwise difficult to synthesise. Reduction of a methyl ether of a phenol by this method, followed by a mild hydrolysis leads to quite useful unsaturated ketones, which may serve as intermediates in the synthesis of naturally occurring substances. ($\pm$)- γ -Curcumene⁹ and ($\pm$)-zingiberene¹⁰ have recently been synthesised by this method. Another unusual application of this method will be found under the section on lanceol (p. 84).

Selenium dioxide and *NBS* may be expected to play a useful role in the field of sesquiterpenes. An important application has been described under β -caryophyllene (p. 88).

The various physical methods have proved quite useful in the terpene field in general. The use of *molecular refractivity* is too well known. Sutherland¹⁴ has further extended the scope of this property by his method of graphical representation.

Ultraviolet spectra have proved very useful in locating two or more carbon—carbon or carbon—oxygen double bonds in conjugation. With the help of Woodward's rules¹² and the exact positions and intensities of the bands, it is possible to get useful information about the degree of substitution in such a system. Several examples will be found in the text. In the azulene series, visible and to some extent the ultraviolet spectra are of great assistance in locating the positions of the nuclear alkyl groups¹³.

In recent times *infra-red spectra* are playing an ever increasing and useful role in organic chemistry in general. The method has two main uses: for the characterisation of the molecule as such, and for the identification of various atomic groupings in a particular compound¹⁴. Sorm and his co-workers¹⁵ have developed a new technique for determining the fundamental type of the sesquiterpenes and their derivatives. The method depends on taking the infra-red spectra of the fully saturated and de-oxygenated hydrocarbon and comparing it with those of the well known types, e.g. perhydrocadinene, perhydrohumulene, etc. Though stereoisomerism was supposed to introduce some complications, the method has been found to be quite useful.

In structure-determination, infra-red spectra can at once indicate the presence or otherwise of various atomic groupings. In detection of ethylenic linkages it has the further advantage of giving some information about the degree of substitution on the double bond¹⁶. For determining the size of an alicyclic ring it is just necessary to determine the carbonyl frequency of that system. Useful application of these procedures will be found under the various sesquiterpenes, e.g. caryophyllene, chigadmarene, etc.

Another great advance in recent times relates to the introduction of *efficient fractionating columns and chromatography* for the isolation of pure substances, as it is of fundamental importance to deal with purest possible samples for the determination of structure. Previous methods, in general, failed to yield analytically pure samples, as the terpenes usually occur as mixtures of closely related substances.

For the present address, the acyclic sesquiterpenes and their derivatives will be taken up first, followed by the monocyclic, bicyclic and tricyclic groups.

ACYCLIC

Farnesene.—The acyclic group of sesquiterpenes, as at present constituted, is a small one and till 1949 only two members, viz., farnesol and nerolidol, were known. Sorm and co-workers¹⁷ isolated an aliphatic sesquiterpene with four double bonds from the essential oil of hops and this constitutes a small percentage of the sesquiterpene fraction. Its separation was effected by repeated chromatography over Al_2O_3 . The earlier workers, who did not have these finer methods of isolation at their disposal, had missed it in the essential oil. On the basis of ozonisation and spectral measurements the compound has been shown to be (I).

(I) Farnesene.

This is identical with β -farnesene, which can be obtained mixed with α -farnesene by the dehydration of farnesol with potassium hydrogen sulphate¹⁸

MONOCYCLIC

The reaction of methylacetylene dicarboxylate with zingiberene has recently been investigated¹⁹. The adduct on pyrolysis yielded a hydrocarbon $C_{10}H_{16}$, identified by its infra-red spectrum as (II), together with dimethyl 4-methylphthalate (III). These results are inconsistent with the earlier structure proposed by Ruzicka and van Veen²⁰ and consequently it has been overthrown in favour of (IV). ($\pm$)-Zingiberene has been synthesised by Mukherji and Bhattacharya^{10,21}.

When zingiberene is treated with Bertram-Walbaum reagent, a bicyclic hydrocarbon, termed *isozingiberene*, is produced. This gives cadalene on dehydrogenation and the position of the two double bonds in the molecule has been established by Soffer, Steinhart, Turner and Stebbins⁴ by employing the labelling technique of Ruzicka and Sternbach, a method which has been briefly outlined in the introduction. *isoZingiberene* is now represented by (V).

(II)

(III)

(IV)

(V)

Curcumenes.— γ - β -Curcymene (VI) occurs in the essential oil from the rhizomes of *Curcuma aromatica*, Salisb. The structure which had been arrived at by Carter, Copp,

Rao, Simonsen and Subramaniam²² as a result of degradative studies, has now been confirmed by its synthesis in the ($\pm$) - form by Birch and Mukherji⁹. Batt and Slater²³ have recently described the isolation and examination of another closely related sesquiterpene, viz. γ -curcumene (VII). Its synthesis has also been achieved by Birch and Mukherji⁹.

These syntheses have been made possible only by the introduction of a new reduction procedure, the scope of which has been briefly discussed earlier.

Humulene.—Humulene, the chief sesquiterpene of the essential oil of hops (from *Humulus lupulus*, L.) has recently been the subject of a number of investigations. Sorm and his collaborators^{17,24} have definitely proved the identity of " α -caryophyllene" with this hydrocarbon, and since it has been shown to be a monocyclic hydrocarbon with no apparent close relationship with β -caryophyllene, the term " α -caryophyllene" should be dropped in preference to humulene. These authors also were the first to show that humulene was a monocyclic hydrocarbon with three ethylenic linkages; they further investigated the hydrogenation and ozonolysis of the compound and prepared a crystalline trioxide, m.p. 122.5° (cf. Ref. 25). Humulene on treatment with Aschan's reagent yields a crystalline, fully saturated tricyclic alcohol, m.p. 116° which appears to be identical with the α -caryophyllene alcohol of Asahina and Tsukamoto²⁵. Recently, very interesting degradation studies have been carried out by Clemo and Harris²⁷. Interesting suggestion^{26,27} has been made that humulene may be represented by (VIII) which represents it as a derivative of cycloundecane. Much further work remains yet to be done to finally settle the question of its constitution.

Lanceol.—Lanceol is a primary monocyclic sesquiterpene alcohol, present in the essential oil from the wood of *Santalum lanceolatum*. Bradfield, Francis, Penfold and Simonsen²⁸, who carried out the initial investigations, represented it provisionally by (IX). On the basis of U. V. spectral measurements and synthetic work, Owen²⁹ deduced evidence which definitely disproved the provisional structure. Recent work by Birch and Murray³⁰ has finally solved this problem. They showed that from the published evidence lanceol may most probably be represented by (X), the $C_{11}H_{14}O_2$ acid obtained on its ozonolysis being best represented by (XI), which must have resulted by a ring-closure of the primary product of ozonolysis, which must be (XII). The

structure (XI) explains all of its properties and on further ozonisation this acid smoothly gives the known acid (XIII). Finally, the structure (XI) has been confirmed by a synthesis.

A crucial proof of the correctness of this structure has been afforded by the hydrogenolysis of lanceol to β -biasabolene (XIV), with sodium and ethanol in liquor ammonia.

B I C Y C L I C

This is an important class of sesquiterpenes and the various hexahydro derivatives of cadalene, eudalene, guaiazulene and vetivazulene fall under this sub-group. Ruzicka, Schinz and Müller³¹ have described the isolation of another new type of bicyclic sesquiterpene from the essential oil of the leaves of *Cedrus atlantica*, Manetti. This hydrocarbon on dehydrogenation furnished a novel naphthalene derivative, $C_{15}H_{16}$, which has not as yet been characterised, though it does not appear to contain an isopropyl group. Recent work at Bangalore³² has shown the presence of another similar type of hydrocarbon in the essential oil from the wood of Himalayan cedar; the new sesquiterpene, α -himachalene appears to be closely related to the hydrocarbon of Ruzicka, Schinz and Müller, but is definitely different from it. Another isomer, β -himachalene, and a tertiary alcohol, himachalol, are also present and yield the same dihydrochloride as is obtained from α -himachalene.

Carotol has been depicted as a derivative of 1:7-dimethyl-4-isopropyl-naphthalene and is a unique specimen in itself. Its chemistry will be shortly discussed.

Besides these types which can be regarded as derivatives of naphthalene and azulenes, various other members represent different bicyclic systems. Important examples are β -caryophyllene and β -santalol.

Cadinene.—Cadinene is one of the most widely distributed sesquiterpenes²²; however, it is likely that many "cadinenes" may be only structural isomers, differing in position of the double bonds about C₁ and C₆.

Cadinene, as regenerated from its dihydrochloride, has recently been shown by Campbell and Soffer³ to possess the structure (XV).

Though the basic structure of cadinene was demonstrated by its dehydrogenation to cadalene by Ruzicka and Meyer²⁴ several decades ago, the location of the double bonds had remained uncertain. Cadinene dioxide (XVI) on interaction with methylmagnesium iodide, followed by dehydration and dehydrogenation with selenium yielded 1 : 2 : 6 : 7-tetramethyl-4-isopropyl-naphthalene (XVII), identified by a synthesis. This, thus, fixes the position of the ethylenic linkages in cadinene between C₁-C₂ and C₆-C₇, as in (XV).

Cadinene on treatment with Bertram-Walbaum mixture, or with formic acid at 100°, etc. yields an isomerised product termed *isocadinene*. Gillam, Moss and West²⁵ have recently shown it to be non-homogeneous, and hence, not a chemical individual as regarded earlier by Robertson and Henderson²⁶.

A *dextro*-rotatory cadinenic sesquiterpene has been isolated from the essential oil of *Hardwickia pinnata*⁶ and shown to be a structural rather than a stereoisomer of *l*-cadinene. On the basis of ozonolysis and dehydrogenation experiments it has been shown to be a mixture of (XVIII) and (XIX); the two isomers could not be separated by fractional distillation.

Sesquibeniene.—The essential oil from *Chamaecyparis formosensis* has been shown by Katsura²⁷ to contain a bicyclic sesquiterpene of the cadalene group. Sesquibeniene, as it has been called, gave formaldehyde on ozonolysis, along with a diketone C₁₃H₂₀O₂ (XX) which on oxidation with cold sodium hypobromite solution gave an acid C₁₂H₁₈O₃ which must be represented by (XXI), as on dehydrogenation it furnished 1-methylnaphthalene. On the basis of these experiments sesquibeniene has been represented by (XXII).

Another sesquiterpene, isolated from the essential oil of the leaves of guava (*Pesidium guayva*) and shown to give cadalene on dehydrogenation, has been provisionally represented by (XXIII) on the basis of its reactions²⁸.

Chigadmarene.—From the essential oil of *Lansium annamalyanum*, Rao, Dutt, Sukh Dev and Guha²⁹ isolated a new bicyclic hydrocarbon, which was shown to belong to the *s*-guaiazulene (XXIV) family. The presence of two ethylenic linkages in the molecule was confirmed by perbenzoic acid titration and quantitative hydrogenation. On the basis of infra-red spectrum it could be deduced that linkages of the type $R_1HC=CR_2R_3$ were absent and an exocyclic double bond was probably present²⁹.

Ozonolysis gave only formaldehyde and a ketone $C_{14}H_{20}O_2$ which has possibly arisen as a result of the ring-closure of the primary product of ozonolysis, $C_{14}H_{22}O_2$. As a result of the various reactions of this diketone, it has been represented by (XXV) and consequently α -chigadmarene by (XXVI).

β -Caryophyllene.— β -Caryophyllene is probably the most widely distributed sesquiterpene occurring in nature⁴¹. It occurs to a considerable extent in the essential oils of *Hardwickia pinnata*⁴² and *Dipterocarpus indicus*⁴³. Very often it occurs along with humulene.

β -Caryophyllene is one of the most widely investigated hydrocarbons, but notwithstanding the number of well known chemists who attacked the problem, the terpene evaded all attempts at structure elucidation till very recently. Dehydrogenation could not give any clue about its carbon framework. The degradation studies⁴⁴ began in 1908 or so, culminated in 1951 in the establishment of its structure, which is unique in the sense that this is the first known derivative of cyclononane occurring in nature.

New trends in the investigation of this sesquiterpene began with the publication of a paper by Treibs⁴⁵ on the oxidation of β -caryophyllene with hydrogen peroxide in the presence of vanadium pentoxide to the crystalline epoxide. This can also be prepared by the action of perbenzoic acid or on auto-oxidation. The oxide has been shown to occur in French lavender oil⁴⁶ and also in the benzene extract of cloves⁴⁷ which is found to be devoid of caryophyllene. Apparently the caryophyllene is formed from this precursor during steam distillation. The caryophyllene-oxide, $C_{15}H_{24}O$, on oxidation with permanganate in acetone solution yielded two isomeric oxido-glycols $C_{13}H_{22}O_2$, and an oxido-ketone $C_{14}H_{22}O_2$, m.p. 61-62°. This oxido-ketone, unexpectedly, did not give the bromoform reaction, a fact which could not be explained on the basis of earlier structures, (XXVII, Ruzicka⁴⁸) and (XXVIII, Rydon⁴⁹) and consequently Treibs proposed the alternative formula (XXIX). There were three more structures proposed depending on the structure of caryophyllenic acid as (XXX) or (XXXI).

(XXVII)

(XXVIII)

(XXIX)

(XXX)

(XXXI)

(XXXII)

(XXXIII)

The presence of a *cyclobutane* ring carrying a *gem*-dimethyl grouping had been fully established in 1936 when ($\pm$)-*trans-norcaryophyllenic acid* (XXXII) was synthesised⁵⁰. A decision about the structure of *caryophyllenic acid* had yet to be arrived at. Barton⁵¹ in 1950 pointed out that the known reactions of *caryophyllenic acid* can be well explained only by the structure (XXX). Confirmation of this view came from three independent sources. Dawson and Ramage⁵² synthesised the alternative acid (XXXI) and found it to be different from *caryophyllenic acid*. An interesting series of reactions by Eschenmoser and Furst⁵³ leading eventually to 4:4-dimethyl*cyclohexanone*, also gave evidence in favour of (XXX), and finally Campbell and Rydon⁵⁴ carried out a straightforward synthesis of the acid (XXX) and proved it to be identical with *caryophyllenic acid* by comparison of the infra-red spectra.

One of the principal and most characteristic degradation products of β -*caryophyllene* is the keto-acid $C_{11}H_{18}O_2$, which on hypobromite oxidation gives *homocaryophyllenic acid*, which has been proved on the basis of synthetic experiments to be (XXXIII)⁵⁵.

Sorm, Dolejs and Pliva⁵⁶ examined infra-red spectrum of the oxido-ketone $C_{14}H_{22}O_2$, of Treibs, referred to above, and by a comparison of the carbonyl frequency (1693 cm^{-1}) with the values known for the *cyclohexanones*, *cycloheptanones*, etc., concluded that the carbonyl group in $C_{14}H_{22}O_2$ probably formed a part of a nine-membered ring. Moreover, dihydro- β -*caryophyllene oxide* by oxidation with loss of two ring-carbon atoms and cyclisation of the resulting dicarboxylic acid gave a ketone $C_{12}H_{20}O_2$ with a band at 1705 cm^{-1} . This clearly showed the presence of a *cycloheptanone* ring in the new ketone and consequently the presence of a *cyclononane* ring in the oxido-ketone was placed on a firm basis. Bearing on this evidence, they suggested a structure of type (XXXIV) for β -*caryophyllene*.

In an important paper, Barton and Lindsey⁵⁷ adduced chemical evidence in favour of the formula (XXXIV). However, further work^{55,58} based on oxidation of the crystalline nitro-nitrosite with permanganate, and especially the structure of *homocaryophyllenic acid*, showed that β -*caryophyllene* is best represented by (XXXV). In terms of this structure, some of the important reactions of β -*caryophyllene* shall be illustrated.

The oxido-ketone of Treibs now must be represented by (XXXVI). This, when refluxed with methanolic potassium hydroxide, gave a highly crystalline, saturated (hence tricyclic) keto-alcohol (XXXVII) which on further oxidation gave an almost quantitative yield of a saturated diketone (XXXVIII). Since this on selenium dioxide oxidation gave the compound (XXXIX), proved on spectroscopic data to contain the chromophone $-\text{C}=\overset{\text{O}}{\text{C}}=\overset{\text{O}}{\text{C}}-\text{CO}-$, the occurrence of the oxygen atoms in (XXXVIII) and consequently in (XXXVII) as 1:4 to each other was placed on a sound evidence. This unsaturated diketone $C_{14}H_{18}O_2$ on oxidation with KMnO_4 in acetone solution or with nitric acid gave a saturated bicyclic dicarboxylic acid $C_{12}H_{18}O_4$, which can be represented by (XL)⁵⁷. The various properties of this acid, e. g. its

facile conversion into an anhydride, resistance to alkaline hydrolysis of its dimethyl ester etc. could easily be explained on the basis of this structure ^{3p-41}.

β -Caryophyllene is known to isomerise readily to tricyclic compounds. It is readily isomerised, for example, by Bertram-Walbaum mixture, or Aschan's reagent or hot formic acid to a saturated tricyclic, crystalline alcohol. On the basis of caryophyllene as (XXXV), this transformation can be readily visualised as taking place as follows; β -caryophyllene alcohol then becomes (XLI). Similarly, the glycol,

$C_{15}H_{26}O_2$ formed as a by-product in the hydrogen peroxide oxidation of β -caryophyllene⁴⁵, can be regarded as (XLII), formed by an electrophilic attack by OH^+ . This glycol on CrO_3 oxidation yielded a crystalline monohydroxy-ketone (XLIII) which was resistant to further oxidation. Wolff-Kishner reduction of this hydroxy-ketone furnished β -caryophyllene alcohol (XLI)

Reasoning similarly, α -caryophyllene alcohol and clovene have been formulated as (XLIV) and (XLV) respectively³⁹.

(XLV)

(XLIV)

The formula of clovene is supported by its infra-red spectrum⁴².

Cadinol.—The term "cadinol" has in general been applied to a *tert*-sesquiterpene alcohol containing two rings which on treatment with gaseous hydrochloric acid gives cadinene dihydrochloride. Cadinols have been isolated from a number of essential oils⁴³. In view of the new structure for cadinene dihydrochloride, α -, β - and γ -cadinols, for example, may be represented by (XLVI), (XLVII), and (XLVIII) respectively.

(XLVI)

(XLVII)

(XLVIII)

Calamendiol.—Calamendiol, $C_{15}H_{26}O_2$, is a crystalline bicyclic sesquiterpene ditertiary alcohol containing one ethylenic linkage, and has been isolated from the essential oil of *Acorus Calamus*⁴⁴.

It has been recently investigated by Treibs⁴⁵. On dehydrogenation it gives cadalene, and ozonolysis yields a crystalline dihydroxyketone, $C_{14}H_{24}O_3$, which does not contain the grouping $-COCH_3$. Dehydration afforded the unsaturated ketone, $C_{14}H_{20}O$, which showed little tendency to isomerise to a phenol. Based on these and similar considerations Treibs has represented calamendiol by (XLIX) when the doubly unsaturated ketone, $C_{14}H_{20}O$, becomes (L). Simonsen⁴⁴ has pointed out that the structure (LI) explains the above reactions equally well and in fact (LII) explains the failure of the ketone to isomerise to a phenol in a better way.

(XLIX)

(LI)

(L)

(LII)

A distinction between the structures (L) and (LII) and consequently between (XLIV) and (LI) can be readily made on the basis of ultraviolet spectrum of the ketone⁴⁶.

Partheniol.—It is a bicyclic sesquiterpene alcohol $C_{15}H_{24}O$, m. p. $127-28^\circ$ of the *s*-guaiazulene family. Its structure has been elucidated by Haagen-Smit and Fong⁶⁷ It occurs as the cinnamate in guayule (*Parthenium argentatum*, Gray).

The tertiary nature of the alcoholic group was readily revealed by its indifference to esterification and ease of dehydration. Dehydrogenation with sulphur yielded *s*-guaiazulene, and hence it remained only to fix the positions of the two double bonds and one tertiary hydroxyl. This was settled by a study of the products of ozonolysis of partheniol and anhydro-tetrahydropartheniol and the application of Blanc's rule to the suitably constituted dicarboxylic acid obtained by stepwise degradation. The structure (LIII) for partheniol, is thus well established.

Carotol.—Carotol, $C_{15}H_{26}O$, occurs in the essential oil of *Daucus carota* L. and it has recently been investigated by Sorm and Urbanek⁶⁸ who have assigned to it the structure (LIV). That it is a derivative of 1:7-dimethyl-4-isopropyl-naphthalene has been established by dehydrogenation over palladised charcoal.

$KMnO_4$ oxidation afforded a crystalline triol (LV) which on cleavage with lead tetra-acetate gave a diketone $C_{13}H_{20}O_3$, m. p. 98° (LVI), containing the $-COCH_3$ grouping. Dehydration of dihydrocarotol, and its ozonolysis and CrO_3 oxidation gave results in support of (LIV).

β -Cyperone.— α -Cyperone, a sesquiterpene ketone, $C_{15}H_{22}O$, of the eudalene series occurs in the essential oil from the tubers of *Cyperus rotundus*⁶⁹, and has been shown to possess the structure (LVII)⁷⁰. On treatment with acid or alkali α -cyperone undergoes a rearrangement to yield another isomeric ketone, β -cyperone, with a higher molecular refractivity and optical rotation. β -Cyperone had been regarded as a stereoisomer of α -cyperone, differing in the disposition of the angular methyl and isopropenyl groups.

McQuillin⁷¹ recently carried out a comparison of the ultraviolet spectra of their derivatives like the oxime, semicarbazone and 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone and

concluded that the two ketones were structural isomers rather than stereoisomers assigning (LVIII) as the most probable structure of β -cyperone.

T R I C Y C L I C

This represents an interesting class of sesquiterpenes and their derivatives. Though a somewhat difficult tract, because of the failure of the dehydrogenation procedure in many cases, yet α -santalol, a tricyclic primary sesquiterpene alcohol, was one of the earliest sesquiterpene derivatives whose constitution could be settled. Recently there has been quite a considerable activity in this field.

Copaene.—In view of the modified structure for cadinene, the structure of copaene, which yields cadinene dihydrochloride on treatment with hydrochloric acid gas, has also been reinvestigated and shown to be (LIX)⁸. Copaene on ozonolysis yields a monobasic ketonic acid, $C_{12}H_{24}O_3$, which can be represented by (LX). This acid on further oxidation with Na hypobromite yielded a dibasic acid regarded by Semmler and Stenzel⁷² as $C_{12}H_{18}O_4$; this is not understandable on the basis of the formulation (LX) for the ketonic acid. This aspect requires reinvestigation⁷³. Another important point has been raised by Birch⁷⁴ who has indicated that (LXI) is one of the several other possible structures which cannot be excluded on the present evidence.

Work now on hand at Bangalore⁷⁵ will soon clarify the situation.

Aromadendrene.—Aromadendrene is the principal sesquiterpene occurring in the eucalyptus oils. It is a tricyclic hydrocarbon with one double bond, which is known to be exocyclic from the various oxidation studies. On dehydrogenation with sulphur it gives *s*-guaiazulene.

Recently Treibs and Barchet⁷⁶ have investigated the problem and have thrown considerable light on its structures. They have put forward the structure (LXII). On ozonolysis it yielded the crystalline ketone $C_{14}H_{22}O$, aromadendrone, which can be represented by (LXIII). Birch⁷⁴ has pointed out a number of objections to this

formula. For example, the action of amyl nitrite on aromadendrone does not yield an oximino derivative but an oximino-carboxylic acid in good yield, and hence probably it does not contain a CH_2 group adjacent to the carbonyl. He has further suggested that aromadendrone can be best represented by (LXIV) when aromadendrone will become (LXV). A determination of the infra-red spectrum of aromadendrone may enable one to distinguish between (LXIII) and (LXV)⁷⁵.

Patchouli Alcohol.—Treibs⁷⁷ has oxidised patchoulene, obtained by the dehydration of the alcohol and has isolated a mixture of camphoric and homocamphoric acid (LXVI). Since patchouli alcohol on dehydrogenation gives *s*-guaiazulene and patchoulene is somewhat difficult to reduce catalytically, he has advanced the structure (LXVII) for the alcohol and (LXVIII) to the dehydration product.

Since patchouli alcohol yields a mixture of hydrocarbons on dehydration, the formula (LXVIII) represents one of the three possible isomers.

Kessyl Alcohol.—Considerable light on its structure has also been thrown by Treibs⁷⁸. Asahina⁷⁹ has shown that kessyl alcohol is a *s*-guaiazulene derivative containing a secondary hydroxyl and an oxide ring. Treibs oxidised the hydroxyl group and the carbonyl, the position of which was fixed by treatment with methylmagnesium iodide, followed by dehydrogenation, when, 5-methylazulene (LXIX) was isolated, the structure of which was deduced on the basis of its absorption spectra. A number of transformations based on the fission of the oxide ring are described and (LXX) is considered to be the most appropriate representation for kessyl alcohol.

Santalols.—The chief constituent of East Indian sandalwood oil is a mixture of two primary alcohols termed α - and β -santalol. The former is tricyclic, whereas the latter is bicyclic in structure, and could have been treated under "bicyclic sesquiterpenes" but due to its close relation to α -santalol, both are best described together.

Santalols (α and β) have recently been obtained in a very pure state⁸⁰.

The structure (LXXI) for α -santalol was arrived at several decades ago by Semmler and Bode⁸¹ and has now been confirmed by a straightforward synthesis by Guha and Bhattacharyya⁸² starting from camphor. Guerbet's acid and α -santalal acid have been shown to be different, a probable structure for the former has been suggested⁸³.

The relationship between α - and β -santalol has been beautifully demonstrated by Bhattacharyya⁸⁴, who has described a direct conversion of α -santalol into β -santalol,

On the basis of degradation studies, two structures, viz. (LXXII, Simonsen³⁵) and (LXXIII; Ruzicka³⁶) for β -santalol have been put forward. The recent synthesis by Bhattacharyya³⁷ confirms the structure by Ruzicka.

C O N C L U S I O N

India, with its variety of climate and soil, is exceptionally rich in the essential oil bearing plants. Sesquiterpenes and their derivatives constitute an important portion of some of these essential oils, e.g. cedar wood oil, gurjun balsam oil, cedrol, etc. It is quite possible that some of these products can find direct application in industry, but it appears to be essential that suitable modifications in the molecular structure of the natural components and their degradation products will have to be carried out to produce more useful materials. The fields of synthetic perfumery material, insecticides, high polymers, etc. appear to be especially promising domains. Further research work will sometime be necessary to settle the structural details of the chief components, before any plan to put them to industrial applications. It will be, however, ideal if any factory, already engaged in the manufacture of synthetics and isolates, could take up such work. This will, however, require a great foresight on the part of the industrial management.

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R E F E R E N C E S

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